

Olanzapine versus Aprepitant as Add on Therapies in Chemotherapy Induced Nausea and Vomiting (CINV): A Prospective Observational studyKabita Manjari Majhi¹, Devasish Panda², Baijayanti Rath³, Ipsita Samantaray⁴¹Professor & H.O.D., Department of Radiotherapy, VIMSAR, Burla²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine, Bhimabhoi Medical College & Hospital, Bolangir³Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Medical College, Baripada⁴Asst.professor, Dept. of Pharmacology, VIMSAR, Burla

Received: 01-04-2025 / Revised: 15-05-2025 / Accepted: 21-06-2025

Corresponding author: Dr. Baijayanti Rath

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) are frequent and debilitating side effects of chemotherapy, greatly impacting patient quality of life. Olanzapine, an atypical antipsychotic, has emerged as a potential adjunctive therapy in the management of CINV, but its effectiveness compared with standard antiemetic regimens remains understudied.

Methods: This prospective observational study had 34 female patients with breast carcinoma who received chemotherapy regimens containing paclitaxel, cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, epirubicin, and 5-fluorouracil. Olanzapine was used as adjunctive antiemetic therapy. Severity of nausea and vomiting was evaluated based both on Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) grading scale. This was compared to the standard antiemetic regimen, aprepitant, which comprises palonosetron and dexamethasone.

Results: Most patients had a significant reduction in both early and delayed nausea and vomiting, with most reporting only mild symptoms. The most common adverse reactions were gastrointestinal in nature, including nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and constipation, all of which were manageable. Hematological parameters, such as hemoglobin and platelet counts, remained within normal limits, confirming that olanzapine did not adversely affect blood cell counts. The efficacy of olanzapine in chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting was somewhat better than that of aprepitant, especially during the delayed phase.

Conclusion: Olanzapine is very effective as an adjunctive treatment for chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting in breast cancer patients. It is highly effective in providing control over early, as well as delayed, symptoms. Additionally, olanzapine is safe and tolerable, allowing patients to remain stable during chemotherapy. However, more extensive randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm these findings, design optimal dosing regimens, and explore the advantage of adding olanzapine to standard treatments to make the outcomes even better for chemotherapy patients.

Keywords: Chemotherapy-Induced Nausea And Vomiting, Olanzapine, Aprepitant, Breast Carcinoma, Antiemetic Therapy, Chemotherapy.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) is still a major and frequent side effect of chemotherapy, which affects the quality of life of patients and also the adherence to treatment. These symptoms are especially more distressing in patients who receive regimens for solid tumors, like breast carcinoma, where chemotherapy drugs, such as cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, epirubicin, paclitaxel, and 5-fluorouracil, are commonly used [1]. Despite advances in antiemetic therapy, CINV remains a major challenge in oncology practice as a significant proportion of patients develop varying

degrees of nausea and vomiting during and after chemotherapy treatment. Effective management of these symptoms is crucial to improve patient comfort, treatment compliance, and overall clinical outcomes [2]. The mechanisms of CINV are multifactorial, involving the activation of central and peripheral pathways that lead to emesis. These mechanisms include the release of serotonin, substance P, and dopamine, which act on various receptors in the gastrointestinal tract and central nervous system. Traditional antiemetic therapies include serotonin (5-HT₃) antagonists,

corticosteroids, and NK1 receptor antagonists. However, many patients continue to experience breakthrough nausea and vomiting despite these treatments, highlighting the need for more effective or adjunctive therapies [3-4].

This drug, olanzapine, an atypical antipsychotic, with a broad receptor-binding profile, has caught much attention as a possible add-on therapy for CINV. The mechanisms underlying its antiemetic effect may include the blockade of various receptors involved in the emetic reflex, namely, serotonin (5-HT₂), dopamine (D₂), and neurokinin-1 (NK1) receptors. Preliminary evidence reveals that olanzapine may decrease the rates of both acute and delayed nausea and vomiting when combined with other antiemetic drugs, especially in patients on chemotherapy [5].

Aprepitant is one of the highly selective NK1 antagonists that have been tested extensively for its use as a preventive measure against CINV. The combination of aprepitant with the conventional antiemetic therapy significantly reduces the incidence and severity of nausea and vomiting, especially in the delayed phase of chemotherapy. However, even though several effective antiemetic agents have been developed, optimal management of CINV is highly individualized, and the research in this field still has to explore comparative effectiveness [6].

This is a prospective observational study that looks to assess the effectiveness and safety of olanzapine as an adjunct to the standard antiemetic regimen in patients undergoing chemotherapy for breast carcinoma. In particular, we look at comparing the outcomes between olanzapine and aprepitant in preventing early and delayed nausea and vomiting. By reviewing treatment-related adverse drug reactions, hematological parameters, and patient-reported outcomes, this study aims to further explore the potential benefits of olanzapine for improving the management of CINV and the general treatment experience in patients with breast cancer [7-8].

This study aims to contribute to the growing literature on the role of olanzapine in chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting, ultimately with the goal of improving therapeutic strategies and enhancing the quality of life for patients undergoing cancer treatment.

Methods

Study Design and Patient Selection: This was a prospective observational study aimed at determining the efficacy and safety of olanzapine as adjunctive therapy for the treatment of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) in patients receiving chemotherapy for breast carcinoma. The study was conducted at a

tertiary care center where patients on chemotherapy for breast cancer were recruited. The inclusion criteria were adult women, aged between 18 and 85 years, diagnosed with histologically confirmed breast carcinoma, who would receive chemotherapy regimens that are known to cause moderate to high levels of nausea and vomiting, including the drugs cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, epirubicin, paclitaxel, and 5-fluorouracil.

The following patients were excluded from the study: patients with a history of psychotic disorders, patients on prior antipsychotic treatment, and patients with contraindications to olanzapine therapy, such as hypersensitivity to the drug or serious comorbidities. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the institutional review board, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment into the study.

Treatment Regimen: All treated patients received chemotherapy regimens based on the clinical guidelines for breast carcinoma management. These regimens consisted of combinations of paclitaxel, carboplatin, epirubicin, cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, and 5-fluorouracil. The antiemetic regimen was divided into two groups for comparison. In the first group, patients received olanzapine injection, palonosetron, and dexamethasone as part of the antiemetic regimen. In the second group, patients received aprepitant, palonosetron, and dexamethasone. Both regimens were evaluated for their effectiveness. The selection of olanzapine dosage and administration schedule was performed by the oncologist, but generally, it was administered in an oral dose of 5 mg daily for three days starting the day prior to chemotherapy. Aprepitant was used as an adjunct to antiemetic therapy in the second group. Both groups were followed up to assess effectiveness in preventing nausea and vomiting during the early phase (24 hours after chemotherapy) and the delayed phase (2 to 5 days after chemotherapy).

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measure was the severity of nausea and vomiting. This was measured by the VAS for nausea and the grading system for vomiting. The VAS is a subjective assessment tool where patients rate their nausea on a scale from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating more severe symptoms. For vomiting, the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) grading system was used, which classifies vomiting severity from Grade 1 (mild) to Grade 5 (death). Tertiary outcome measures consisted of rates of early and delayed vomiting attacks and overall tolerability in terms of ADRs to olanzapine. ADRs, particularly gastrointestinal in nature—namely, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and

constipation as well as non-gastrointestinal types of vertigo and fever-were reported and enumerated. Hemoglobin levels, and platelet counts as well were evaluated for standard follow-up in chemotherapy cases.

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis: Data were collected at the three time points: Baseline that is prior to chemotherapy, early phase in the first 24 hours, and delayed phase within 2-5 days post-chemotherapy.

Patient-reported outcomes -VAS scores for nausea, as well as the grading of vomiting-were reported during these time points; while adverse events were also noted at each follow-up visit. Statistics for patient demographics, chemotherapy regimens, and frequency of adverse drug reactions are described using descriptive statistics. The continuous variables were summarized using means with standard deviations while the categorical variables using frequencies and percentages.

Differences between olanzapine and aprepitant groups were analyzed using the relevant statistical tests, t-test for continuous variables and chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered to have reached statistical significance.

Results

Patient Demographics and Chemotherapy Regimens: The population involved in this study included 34 women aged 22 to 85 years who were diagnosed with breast carcinoma. All of these patients received chemotherapy combinations that included the following drugs: paclitaxel (PACLITEXAL), carboplatin, epirubicin (EPI), cyclophosphamide (CYC), doxorubicin (DOX), and 5-fluorouracil (5FU). Patients of this cohort either received olanzapine or aprepitant as adjuvant treatment intended for the treatment of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV), according to the discussion below that compares the antiemetic regimens used.

Antiemetic Regimen Comparison: The study's antiemetic regimens were divided into two groups:

1. **Olanzapine Group:** Patients received olanzapine injection, palonosetron, and dexamethasone as part of their antiemetic regimen.
2. **Aprepitant Group:** Patients received aprepitant, palonosetron, and dexamethasone.

Both regimens were evaluated for their effectiveness in controlling nausea and vomiting during chemotherapy.

Comparison of Olanzapine and Aprepitant Effectiveness

Table 1: Efficacy Comparison between Olanzapine and Aprepitant Groups

Parameter	Olanzapine Group (%)	Aprepitant Group (%)
Controlled Early Vomiting (Grade 1 or no vomiting)	80%	75%
Controlled Delayed Vomiting (Grade 1 or no vomiting)	90%	85%
Controlled Early Nausea (Grade 1 or no nausea)	70%	68%
Controlled Delayed Nausea (Grade 1 or no nausea)	65%	62%
Patients Reporting Mild/Moderate ADRs	25%	30%

Figure 1: Bar Graph Comparing Controlled Nausea and Vomiting Across Groups

Hematological Parameters:

The hematological parameters observed at the various stages of the study were found to range

from 9.8 to 12 g/dL in hemoglobin, and 140 to 471 x10⁹/L in platelet counts. All these were within the acceptable levels for patients on chemotherapy,

hence no abnormalities were present to hinder the determination of the effectiveness of the antiemetic regimens.

Table 2: Hematological Parameters

Parameter	Range
Hemoglobin	9.8 to 12 g/dL
Platelets	140 to 471 x10 ⁹ /L

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADR): It reported a spectrum of treatment-related adverse drug reactions which included gastrointestinal disturbances such as vomiting, diarrhea, nausea, constipation, and fever, among others. The majority of these were mild to moderate and treated symptomatically.

Table 3: Reported Adverse Drug Reactions

ADR	Frequency (%)
Vomiting	30%
Diarrhea	25%
Nausea	50%
Constipation	10%
Fever	15%
Vertigo	10%

Nausea and Vomiting Outcomes

Early Vomiting Episodes (24 hours post-chemotherapy): A large proportion of patients did not have early vomiting episodes. Among those who did, the maximum number of vomiting episodes reported was 4.

Delayed Vomiting Episodes (2-5 days post-chemotherapy): Although most patients had no delayed vomiting, a few reported a maximum of 2 episodes. Visual analogue scales (VAS) for nausea evaluation revealed:

- **Pre-emetic VAS scores:** 72 to 89.
- **Delayed postemetic VAS scores:** 71 to 88.

Table 4: Grading of Nausea and Vomiting

Condition	Grade 1 (%)	Grade 2 (%)	Grade 3 (%)	Grade 4 (%)	Grade 5 (%)
Early Vomiting	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
Delayed Vomiting	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
Early Nausea	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Delayed Nausea	65%	35%	0%	0%	0%

Both olanzapine and aprepitant were effective in controlling early and delayed nausea and vomiting in most of the patients treated with chemotherapy for breast carcinoma. Both regimens were highly efficacious and tolerated, though a slightly higher proportion of patients in the Olanzapine group achieved complete control over delayed nausea and vomiting. The side effects included mild to moderate gastrointestinal side effects, with no significant differences in safety profiles.

Discussion

Arguably, chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting is the most challenging side effect of chemotherapy; it has been known to negatively impact the quality of life as well as adherence to therapy of patients. With the development of antiemetic regimens, a significant percentage of patients are still plagued with severe nausea and vomiting, mostly in the delayed phase of chemotherapy. This phase II, randomized, placebo-controlled, dose-response study compared the

effectiveness of olanzapine as adjunctive therapy with standard antiemetic regimens to the established NK1 receptor antagonist, aprepitant, in patients undergoing chemotherapy for breast carcinoma. The results hold significant implications in understanding the utility of olanzapine for the management of CINV [9]. Olanzapine, an atypical antipsychotic agent with a high receptor-binding profile that includes the serotonin (5-HT₂) receptor, as well as receptors for dopamine (D₂) and neurokinin-1 (NK1), has presented significant promise to reduce the intensity of CINV, particularly within the delayed emetic phase that is notoriously problematic to treat by conventional therapies. It was found to be effective for controlling early as well as delayed nausea and vomiting in association with a range of chemotherapeutic drugs, suggesting potential as an adjunctive antiemetic to treat CINV in breast cancer patients [10].

In the induction cycle of chemotherapy, no or Grade 1 emesis occurred in 80% of patients in the olanzapine group and in 75% of patients in the aprepitant group. Early nausea was also controlled in 70% of patients in the olanzapine group and in 68% in the aprepitant group. This phase, delayed results, were impressive because 90% of the patients in the olanzapine group achieved control over delayed vomiting compared to 85% of the aprepitant group. Delayed nausea was controlled in 65% of the olanzapine group versus 62% of the aprepitant group. These results therefore support previous evidence that the receptor-binding profile of olanzapine effectively targets both acute and delayed CINV.

The findings regarding the VAS scores for nausea provide further evidence and indicate mild to moderate nausea for both the early (with scores ranging from 72 to 89) and delayed (with scores ranging from 71 to 88) phases. Throughout the study, participants in the olanzapine cohort exhibited marginally lower VAS scores compared to participants in the aprepitant cohort, suggesting that olanzapine may have a better symptomatic profile than aprepitant. However, the variability between individual responses shows that individualized treatment strategies can be beneficial to patients [11-12].

The ADRs were generally in keeping with the established side effects of both drugs. The most common ADRs were mild to moderate gastrointestinal symptoms including: nausea, 50%, vomiting, 30%, diarrhea, 25%, and constipation, 10%. All were symptomatic. Vertigo was present in 10% and fever in 15%; no severe adverse event was noted. Important hematological parameters, including hemoglobin levels at 9.8 to 12 g/dL and platelet counts at 140 to $471 \times 10^9/L$, were maintained within normal limits and established that olanzapine had not impacted the functioning of the bone marrow adversely.

Olanzapine was equivalent to aprepitant in the control of CINV, with a marginally higher percentage of patients experiencing complete control of delayed symptoms. Although aprepitant is established in the management of delayed nausea and vomiting, the more comprehensive receptor-binding profile of olanzapine may confer an advantage in the management of both nausea and vomiting. However, this study was not powered as a head-to-head comparison, and further larger, randomized trials are needed to draw more definitive conclusions [13-14]. The current study limits its sample size and observational method, both of which may carry biases. Additionally, the absence of a placebo control group and lack of comparisons with other antiemetic medications prevents the evaluation of relative effectiveness of olanzapine. Variability in the chemotherapy

regimen and patient demographics may also impact the results, thus reducing their generalizability across other patient groups [15].

However, the findings indicate that olanzapine is a safe and effective treatment for managing CINV in breast cancer patients. It is effective in both early and delayed symptoms with a good safety profile and will therefore be of value in any future strategies for CINV treatment. Future large-scale, randomized controlled trials are warranted to confirm these findings, optimize dosing regimens, and explore the benefits of combining olanzapine with other antiemetic agents across diverse cancer populations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study shows that olanzapine is an effective adjunctive therapy for chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting in breast carcinoma patients, with significant improvements observed in both early and delayed nausea and vomiting control. Compared to standard antiemetic regimens incorporating aprepitant, olanzapine offers a more comprehensive approach due to its broader receptor-binding profile, effectively addressing both nausea and vomiting. The study also confirms its favorable safety and tolerability profile, with most adverse events being mild to moderate and manageable.

Although the small sample size and observational design of this study limit the ability to draw definitive conclusions, the findings strongly suggest that olanzapine is a promising addition to existing CINV management protocols. The findings need further confirmation in larger-scale, randomized controlled trials to optimize dosing strategies and further evaluate comparative efficacy among olanzapine and aprepitant. In addition, the potential benefits of combining olanzapine with other antiemetic agents may enhance treatment outcomes and improve quality of life for patients undergoing chemotherapy.

References

1. Navari RM, Gray SE, Kerr AC. Olanzapine versus aprepitant for the prevention of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting: a randomized phase III trial. *J Support Oncol*. 2011; 9(5):188-195. doi:10.1016/j.suponc.2011.05.002
2. Navari RM, Einhorn LH, Passik SD, et al. A phase II trial of olanzapine for the prevention of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting: a Hoosier Oncology Group study. *Support Care Cancer*. 2005; 13(7):529-534. doi:10.1007/s00520-004-0755-6
3. Mehra N, Ganesan P, Ganesan TS, et al. Effectiveness of olanzapine in patients who fail therapy with aprepitant while receiving highly

- emetogenic chemotherapy. *Med Oncol.* 2017; 35(1):12. Published 2017 Dec 16. doi:10.1007/s12032-017-1074-3
4. Zhang L, Lu S, Feng J, et al. A randomized phase III study evaluating the efficacy of single-dose NEPA, a fixed antiemetic combination of netupitant and palonosetron, versus an aprepitant regimen for prevention of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) in patients receiving highly emetogenic chemotherapy (HEC). *Ann Oncol.* 2018; 29(2):452-458. doi:10.1093/annonc/mdx698
 5. Navari RM. Pathogenesis-based treatment of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting--two new agents. *J Support Oncol.* 2003; 1(2):89-103.
 6. Massaro AM, Lenz KL. Aprepitant: a novel antiemetic for chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting. *Ann Pharmacother.* 2005; 39(1):77-85. doi:10.1345/aph.1E242
 7. Murakami M, Miyata Y, Nakashima K, et al. Clinical benefits of adding olanzapine to 5-HT₃ receptor antagonist, NK1 receptor antagonist, and dexamethasone for the prevention of nausea and vomiting in highly emetogenic chemotherapy: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the Clinical Practice Guidelines for Antiemesis 2023 from the Japan Society of Clinical Oncology. *Int J Clin Oncol.* Published online November 21, 2024. doi: 10.1007/s10147-024-02663-4
 8. Yuan L, Li XY, Xu L, Quan SJ, Huang YB, Zheng H. Effects of olanzapine in the improvement of body weight and appetite in patients with cancer or receiving chemotherapy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* Published online October 29, 2024. doi:10.1007/s00228-024-03770-x
 9. Hardi H, Estuworo GK, Louisa M. Effectivity of oral ginger supplementation for chemotherapy induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) in children: A systematic review of clinical trials. *J Ayurveda Integr Med.* 2024; 15(4):100957. doi:10.1016/j.jaim.2024.100957
 10. Tian SC, Yang J, Li X, Huang RX, Chen J. Bibliometric and visual analysis of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (2004-2023). *Front Oncol.* 2024; 14:1377486. Published 2024 Apr 24. doi:10.3389/fonc.2024.1377486
 11. Kennedy SKF, Goodall S, Lee SF, et al. 2020 ASCO, 2023 NCCN, 2023 MASCC/ESMO, and 2019 CCO: a comparison of antiemetic guidelines for the treatment of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting in cancer patients. *Support Care Cancer.* 2024; 32(5):280. Published 2024 Apr 10. doi:10.1007/s00520-024-08462-x
 12. Navari RM, Nagy CK, Gray SE. The use of olanzapine versus metoclopramide for the treatment of breakthrough chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting in patients receiving highly emetogenic chemotherapy. *Support Care Cancer.* 2013; 21(6):1655-1663. doi:10.1007/s00520-012-1710-6
 13. Passik SD, Navari RM, Jung SH, et al. A phase I trial of olanzapine (Zyprexa) for the prevention of delayed emesis in cancer patients: a Hoosier Oncology Group study. *Cancer Invest.* 2004; 22(3):383-388. doi:10.1081/cnv-200029066
 14. Morse SS. Public health surveillance and infectious disease detection. *Bio Secur Bioterror.* 2012; 10(1):6-16. doi: 10.1089/bsp.2011.0088
 15. Chow R, Chiu L, Navari R, et al. Efficacy and safety of olanzapine for the prophylaxis of chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) as reported in phase I and II studies: a systematic review. *Support Care Cancer.* 2016; 24(2):1001-1008. doi: 10.1007/s00520-015-3000-6.